

Contrasting processes driving tropical and non-tropical winter warm spells

1. Codes information

Code to identify warm spells in the cold season (i.e., winter warm spells). We have uploaded all data and codes to generate the figures (i.e., Figure 1–5 in the manuscript).

2. Data information

2.1 Winter warm spells

See Methods section of the paper for a detailed description about how to identify the winter warm spells. The data uploaded are yearly series of the observed frequency (events), participating days (days), maximum duration (days), mean duration (days), maximum intensity (°C), and mean intensity (°C) of the winter warm spells and the occurrence dates of warm spells.

2.2 Raw datasets

Due to size of the original raw datasets used in this paper, we only provide the URLs to download these datasets. Data analyzed in the paper is publicly available from the following sources: The ERA5 reanalysis dataset at single level can be downloaded from <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/datasets/reanalysis-era5-single-levels?tab=overview>, and the pressure levels are publicly available via <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/datasets/reanalysis-era5-pressure-levels?tab=overview>.